

University of Stuttgart
Stuttgart Wind Energy (SWE)
@ Institute of Aircraft Design

Evolution of the SWE Research Lidar Scanner

IEA TASK 52 – General Meeting

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Kassel; 23.09.2025

The SWE Lidar Team

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A SWE Vision

Drones

Measure local high res wind speed and do visual blade inspection

Sensor fusion

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01010100

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Microphones

Measure sound emissions and propagation

Lidars

Can replace met masts and measure wind speed and wind direction over short range and large areas

Smart site assessment

The ideal wind farm site and turbine location is optimized

Smart simulation and design

The turbine design and wind farm layout are optimized site specifically

Smart operation and control

Wind farm optimizes its power generation to balance best power generation with least social impact. It also generates power forecasts.

Smart maintenance and lifetime extension

Wind farm optimizes its own maintenance and lifetime schedule

UAV - ANDroMeDa

[SWE]

- Weight: 5300g
- Flight time of 15-20min
- Maximum wind speed: $15 \frac{m}{s}$
- Maximum vertical speed: $8 \frac{m}{s}$

University of Stuttgart – Stuttgart Wind Energy (SWE)

Probably the smallest lidar manufacturer in the world...

- SWE Scanning Lidar 2.0
Onshore version

- SWE Scanning Lidar 2.1
Offshore version

- SWE Scanning Lidar 1.0 (first generation; no longer in operation)

A little bit of history.

The early years...

**SWE Lidar Scanner 1.0
(1st generation)**

SWE Lidar Scanner 1.0 – System

- 2007: Standard Windcube™ system from Leosphere™ (ground based)
 - Range 40m - 200m
 - Spatial resolution 26m
 - Speed accuracy 0.1m/s

SWE Lidar Scanner 1.0 – Scanner Development

- Scanner system
 - Angle of projection 53,2°
 - Flexible trajectories
 - High speed and acceleration
 - Repeatability accuracy
 - Adaptable to Windcube system

Scanner: single mirror with 2DOF

[Fig. SWE]

Rotation stages

Lightweight frame
and mirror

Carbon fiber rods,
additionally braided

Stuttgarter Wind Energy (SWE) ...

... probably the smallest wind lidar “manufacturer” in the world

- “SWE Lidar Scanner 1.0” (2009 – 2018)
- Development and testing in the RAVE project “Lidar I”
- Basis: Leosphere Windcube V1
- 2D mirror kinematics for laser deflection

SWE Lidar Scanner 1.0 – Main Trajectories

Staring mode
(1D)

Sliding mode (2D)

Circle (3D)

Liss2Grid (3D)

[Fig. SWE]

SWE Lidar Scanner 1.0 – Examples

[SWE]

SWE Lidar Scanner 1.0

Deployment worldwide

- Onshore campaigns

- Bremerhaven 05/2009 – 03/2010
- Risø–DTU 04/2011 – 01/2012
- Grevesmuehlen 05/2013 – 04/2014
- NREL – NWTC 2012, 2014, 2015
- ...

- Offshore campaigns

- Alpha Ventus
- Baltic I
- ...

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SWE Lidar Scanner 1.0

Deployment in RAVE projects

- Onshore campaigns

- Bremerhaven 05/2009 – 03/2010
- Risø–DTU 04/2011 – 01/2012
- Grevesmuehlen 05/2013 – 04/2014
- NREL – NWTC 2012, 2014, 2015
- ...

- Offshore campaigns

- [Alpha Ventus](#)
- Baltic I
- ...

[SWE]

SWE Lidar Scanner 1.0 – Measurement Campaigns / Field Testing

Lidar Assisted Collective Pitch Control

[SWE]

National Wind Technology Center
Boulder, Colorado, USA
from March to August 2012

- CART2: SWE-Scanner 1.0
- Goal: minimization of generator speed variation

→ proof of LAC concept !

Schlipf, D.; Fleming, P.; Haizmann, F.; Scholbrock, A.; Hofsäß, M.; Wright, A.; Cheng, P.W.: *Field Testing of Feedforward Collective Pitch Control on the CART2 Using a Nacelle-Based Lidar Scanner*, TORQUE, 2012

The past few years...

**SWE Lidar Scanner 2.0
(2nd generation)**

Development of a Robust Nacelle-Based Scanning Lidar System (1/2)

From „Lidar I“ to „ANWIND“...

<p>„Lidar I“</p>	<p>Stuttgart Wind Energy (SWE) Lidar Scanner 1.0</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ flexible trajectories (7 x 7 grid) ➤ high speed / acceleration ➤ big / heavy / unreliable (offshore) ➤ measurement range: ~ 200 m ➤ limitations in software („black box“)
<p>„Lidar II“</p>	<p>Whirlwind 1 Lidar (OpticSense GmbH, Uni Oldenburg)</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ small / light ➤ very robust ➤ measurement range: ~ 400 m ➤ not scanning
<p>ANWIND</p>	<p>Stuttgart Wind Energy (SWE) Lidar Scanner 2.0</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ small / light: D=350; L=610; m=45 kg ➤ number of measurement planes: 1-37 ➤ very large scanning angles: +-26,6° ➤ measurement range: ~ 555 m ➤ highly flexible trajectories ➤ several very fast scanning modes

Development of a Robust Nacelle-Based Scanning Lidar System (2/2)

A mechatronic component for Wind Turbine Control

[SWE]

Stuttgart Wind Energy (SWE) Lidar Scanner 2.0

- improve robustness & compactness
- beyond state-of-the-art specifications
- focus on **research** & control applications (increase TRL of Lidar-Assisted Control)

- mechatronic engineering design
- reliability engineering
- optimize overall system („Systems Engineering“)

(Pulsed) Nacelle-Based Scanning Lidar System

SWE Lidar Scanner 2.0 – ONSHORE Version

Specifications:

- Dimensions (D x L): (\emptyset 350 x 620) mm
- Weight: 45 kg
- 24 V DC power supply (max. 80 W)
- Measurement range: $x_{\min} = 45$ m; $x_{\max} = 885$ m
(depending on environmental conditions)
- Number of measurement planes: 59 (Δ freely configurable)
- Range of azimuth- / elevation-angle: $\pm 26,6^\circ$
- User-defined measurement trajectories
- Several very fast scanning modes

(Pulsed) Nacelle-Based Scanning Lidar System

Examples of customizable scanning patterns

Stuttgart Wind Energy (SWE) Lidar Scanner 2.0

[SWE]

Nowadays...

**SWE Lidar Scanner 2.1
(offshore version)**

Currently Under Development:

SWE Lidar Scanner 2.1 – OFFSHORE Version

Target specifications:

- Dimensions (D x L): (\varnothing 370 x 720) mm
- Weight: < 30 kg
- Measurement range: $x_{\min} = 45$ m; $x_{\max} = 885$ m
(depending on environmental conditions)
- Number of measurement planes: = 59 (Δ **freely configurable**)
- Range of azimuth- / elevation-angle: $\pm 26,6^\circ$
- User-defined measurement trajectories
- Several very fast scanning modes
- Increase robustness, high reliability and high MTBF, built for harsh offshore environment and large motion conditions of floating wind turbines and floating lidar systems

Field testing

SWE Scannig Lidar 2.0 vs. Met Mast Ultrasonic-Anemometer

At test site „WINSENT“ (southern Germany)

Project „NEOWIND“

Task 2.1 Hardware development and integration of an offshore prototype of the Scanning Lidar (Project partner: EOLOS – Floating Lidar Solutions)

- Assembled offshore prototype on a floating lidar buoy

Project „ABBA“

With WETI Flensburg (Prof. David Schlipf)

- To be developed and tested:

LAC (Lidar assisted control) with SWE Scanning Lidar 2.0

Projekt „EMUwind“

Multi Sensor Measurement Campaign @ GE/Rotterdam

- Met mast:
Position of SWE Lidar Scanner 2
@ ~ 85m

- Haliade-X:
Position of SWE Lidar Scanner 1
@ ~ 140m

Summary

Summary

SWE Lidar Scanner 2.X

- Powerful, compact and flexible scanning lidar for processing research questions or special industrial projects
 - Platform for newly developed concepts / algorithms
 - Lidar Assisted Control (LAC)
 - Smart monitoring strategies
 - Power curve validation
 - Investigation underperforming of wind turbines/wind farms
 - Multi-Lidar scanning
 - Wind field measurement using multi-sensor networks (+UAVs +conventional measurement technology)
- SWE should be prepared for the challenges of future projects!

University of Stuttgart

Thank you!

Questions? Need more information? Get in touch with us!

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